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Thermal Solutions for Green Buildings

Deliverable D2.3

Model for quality control and optimization of solid wood and fibre impregnation with

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Summary

The objective of the work in Deliverable 2.3 was to optimize the impregnation parameters, weight percentage gain of the selected bioPCM (i.e., ethyl palmitate, EP) and thermal characteristics; the above parameters were elaborated in models for prediction and control of the impregnation quality in solid wood and fibres. BioPCM retention was optimized following the outcomes of the Tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 as well as the feedback from WP4.

The effect of thermal modification (TM) and microwave treatment (MW) on solid wood lamellae were studied comprehensively by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the compound middle lamellae (CML) found the most susceptible part of the wood cell wall to be modified in form of checks, buckling and delamination. The above micro changes ensure additional retention of EP when impregnated, which was proven initially in Deliverable 2.1. The impregnated wood fibres were studied by light microscopy and two dyes to visualise the penetration and location of EP in the wood cells. Due to the properties of the impregnated bioPCM, it was hypothesized in Deliverable 2.2 that EP cannot penetrate the nanopores in the wood cell wall and the main transport path during impregnation found to be through the cell wall openings (pits); a fact proven by microscopy observations. Quantification of EP in fibres was difficult because it is highly variable and depends on the wood species, anatomical elements and physical status of fibre (torn, damaged or relatively untouched after refining).

Two approaches were applied to model the impregnation of solid wood lamellae. Impregnation process of phase change material in wood lamellae was theoretically modelled by using a Washburn equation and adapted further to macroscopic model where the wood pore size distribution data obtained from X-ray micro-computer tomography (CT) were employed. The model was calibrated and verified using experimental results of ethyl palmitate impregnation of Scots pine sapwood. The model allows selection of impregnation parameters (pressure, duration) and calculates the retention of EP in solid wood. The second statistical modelling analysed data of 9 impregnations to show the relations between density, weight percentage gain and leaching of EP. Both models revealed that porosity and wood density are the property that determine the amount of impregnated EP while leaching is related to the impregnation parameters. Deliverable 2.3 contributes with the two models that can be used for practical impregnations of EP but also can be adjusted to other wood species and liquids.

A computational fluid mechanics (CFM) model was developed to demonstrate the impregnation of EP in a single spruce fiber. The simulations revealed clear differences between early- and latewood fibre impregnation behaviour arising from pit geometry and flow resistance. Importantly, the surface tension and capillary effects increased as lumen filling progressed and significantly influenced the impregnation efficiency.

Impregnated lamellae with various retention of EP were combined to imitate the middle layer of parquet and tested regarding thermal performance of the impregnated bioPCM by measuring material's T-history. The measured melting enthalpy corresponded well to the calculated values. Deliverable 2.3 completes the work in WP2 and contributes to the understanding of the chain from the initial biomaterial (solid wood and fibres), the pre-treatments to improve permeability and impregnability, and selection of appropriate impregnation schedule to ensure an optimal amount of EP as a source of thermal energy storage in building materials.

1. Introduction

Deliverable 2.3 “Model for quality control and optimization of solid wood and fibre impregnation with bioPCM” is a part of WP2 and based on the work in Task 2.4 “Modelling and quality control of the products impregnated with bioPCM”.

This report comprises the work aiming at *optimizing the impregnation parameters, weight percentage gain of the selected bioPCM (ethyl palmitate) and thermal characteristics; the above parameters to be elaborated in a model for prediction and control of the impregnation quality. BioPCM retention was continuously optimized following the outcomes of the Tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 as well as the feedback from WP4. Degree of impregnation is quantified by digital light and scanning electron microscopy. Impregnated fibres were isolated, stained, imaged and analysed with an image analysis software. Selected samples were also tested regarding thermal performance of the impregnated bioPCM.*

Limitations

Modelling in Deliverable 2.3 is limited mainly to impregnation of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) and, consequently, to the anatomical-physical properties of this wood species. However, the findings and conclusions can be applied to other wood species when their cell morphology and properties are inserted in the model. Only a theoretically undamaged Norway spruce fibre was used in the CFM model. The emphasis in Deliverable 2.3 is limited to wood treatment by impregnation of a particular phase change material, i.e., ethyl palmitate in wood lamellae with pre-defined dimensions and softwood tracheids (fibres). The study does not consider water transport and interactions as most of the impregnation model studies.

2. Understanding the effect of microstructural changes caused by microwave and thermal modification on wood impregnation

Thermal modification (TM) in vacuum was applied after the solid wood was dried to almost absolute dry weight while the microwave irradiation (MW) was applied to wood at low moisture content (ca. 8-10%, Deliverable D2.1). In both cases the intent with selection of low moisture content was to avoid the destructive forces caused by rapid evaporation of water leading to steam pressure in the wood structure. It has been shown that the force destroys wood rays causing macro checks (Treu and Gjølsjø, 2008, Torgovnikov and Vinden 2009).

Regarding the effect of TM and MW treatments on the impregnability of solid softwood (expressed as WPG) with EP, the analysis in Deliverable D2.1 showed that spruce wood increased significantly the WPG in comparison to the control untreated samples. Scots pine did not show increased impregnability neither by TM nor by MW (Table 1 below from Deliverable 2.1). TM is a more effective way than MW to increase the permeability and impregnability of three of the studied wood species, the effect is measurable in the range 180-210°C for spruce and poplar and at 210°C for beech wood.

Table 1. Treatment effects of MW and TM significant at 95% pair-wise confidence interval for the variable weight percentage gain (WPG); p -values < 0.05. * – absorbed energy.

Species	Significant pairs WPG
Spruce	Control – MW (8.4 kW) * Control – TM 180°C Control – TM 200°C Control – TM 210°C
Pine	none
Beech	Control – TM 210°C
Poplar	Control – MW (6.25 kW) * Control – TM 180°C Control – TM 200°C Control – TM 210°C

The most pronounced action of the elevated temperature and microwaves is found in the compound middle lamella in addition to possibly forming larger checks in the wood through over heating/swelling of the wood of specific regions. In the present Deliverable 2.3 we undertake deeper analysis of the treatment effects on the anatomical structure of the four species (spruce, Scots pine, poplar and beech) based on advanced scanning and environmental scanning electron microscopy.

2.1 Spruce wood

Observations on TM and MW irradiated Norway spruce samples proved that at least part of the MW irradiation was concentrated in the compound middle lamella (CML) regions between tracheids, which showed considerable disruption while the tracheid S2 cell wall layer appeared undamaged (Figure 1). The compound middle lamellae is a weak point in the cell wall structure and checks along the CML are clearly visible.

The effects of both modifications are also demonstrated in the radial- and tangential longitudinal sections (RLS and TLS) of the wood structure (Figure 2). The images showed places in the anatomical structure with no visible changes and undamaged bordered pits. Other parts of the structure can demonstrate damaged bordered pits with delamination and remains of the pit apertures (Figure 2c). The revealed micro checks in the compound middle lamella are 1-3 μm wide.

A previous study of Bernabei and Salvatici (2016) demonstrated a typical pattern of spruce cell wall deformations characterised by an initial swelling stage observed at temperature of 100-110°C. Although the above temperature is low and the process is considered as drying rather than thermal modification, blisters in cell corners of CML have been observed by environmental scanning electron microscopy (ESEM). The observation can partly be explained by an increase pressure caused by vapour from evaporation of bound water or gases, e.g., evaporation of acids by hydrolyses of hemicelluloses during the thermal destruction (Fengel and Wegener 1989). The temperature interval 110-145°C corresponds also to the beginning of glass transition temperature of lignin in softwood (Poletto 2017). Our study confirmed the *in-situ* observation of Bernabei and Salvatici (2016) by demonstrating the artefacts of bluster expansions, namely the indentations in the corners of CML (Figure 1e).

Figure 1. SEM images of untreated control sample, TM and MW modified spruce wood. Transverse sections (TS) of untreated spruce wood (a) and cell wall middle lamella between four axial tracheids (b). Transverse sections of earlywood tracheids with large checks along the CML between adjacent tracheids in both c) and d). TS section of TM spruce at 210°C showing indentations of various sizes in the outer secondary wall/middle lamella regions between axial tracheids (e).

Figure 2. SEM images of untreated control sample, TM and MW modified spruce wood. RLS of untreated wood (a) and MW treated wood (b) with checks in the compound middle lamellae between parenchyma cells in a uniseriate wood ray. Remains of pit apertures (c) probably destroyed by MW and micro checks in the middle lamella between adjacent tracheids after MW treatment (c and d) and in TLS of thermally modified axial tracheids with checking in the CML (e).

2.2 Scots pine sapwood

A comparison of untreated, MW and thermally modified wood of Scots pine sapwood is shown in [Figure 3](#). No checks and delamination in the compound middle lamellae were observed in the untreated samples, see [Figures 3a, b, and c](#). Small checks and buckling in the compound middle lamella appears in transverse sections of wood after MW treatment ([Figure 3d, e](#)). The effect of MW is less pronounced without large checks compared to those observed in spruce ([Figure 1c, d](#)). There is no evidence that MW irradiation disrupts the window and/or bordered pits, i.e., no difference was found when compared to the untreated wood ([Figure 3f](#)). The checking in the middle

lamellae region is also observed in TLS sections (Figure 3g, h) and RLS with delamination in the space between pits (Figure 3i).

Figure 3. Micrographs of untreated control and MW modified Scots pine samples. TS of untreated wood (a) and MW treated wood (d, e) with checks in the compound middle lamellae between the tracheids. Bordered pits (f) with no visible changes caused by MW. Checks in TLS (g) and RLS (h) and longitudinal checks along the pit aperture and further into the CML/S2 layer (i).

The SEM observations on spruce and Scots pine wood after MW treatment can be summarised as significant changes in the CML that were more numerable and pronounced in spruce than in Scots pine wood. The above can be explained by the sensitivity of the CML with its lower density due to highest lignin concentration in the cell wall and the irregular orientation of the cellulose microfibrils in the primary walls. Poorly or non-lignified cell corners (Daniel *et al.* 1991) can be another explanation of the observed changes. The checks may follow along the pit aperture and further into the CML/S2 layer (Figure 3i).

Changes in Scots pine CML after TM are more discrete and appear as buckling and indentations along the circumference of the CML (Figure 4a, b, c). In RLS and TLS the checks in the CML of adjacent tracheids (Figure 4d, c) look similar to those in spruce. It is difficult to interpret the effect of the MW and TM on the bordered pits; however, some irregular delamination of the pit apertures of the pits were occasionally apparent.

Figure 4. Changes in the cell wall structure of Scots pine wood after TM. Buckling (a, b) and indentations, particularly in the cell corners (c). Typical checking of CML between adjacent tracheids in RL- and TLS (d, e).

The increase in the wood porosity after MW and TM and, consequently, retention of the impregnated phase material proven by pycnometry and X-ray computer tomography is explained by the SEM observations. The retention increase takes place through the induced checks, indentations and buckling in the compound ML between the wood cells – any combination is possible, e.g., between adjacent tracheids, parenchyma, tracheid-parenchyma cells. Large macro checks were also observed after the MW treatment, that follow the orientation of the wood rays in radial direction. The observed structural changes facilitate not only the penetration of any liquid by impregnation but also contribute to the decrease of the mechanical properties after both microwave and thermal modification treatment (Torgovnikov and Vinden 2009, Esteves and Pereira 2009).

2.3 Poplar and beech wood

Although not considered as proper candidates for impregnation with PCM and flooring processing, poplar and beech have been studied to follow the microstructural changes caused by MW and TM of hardwoods. The observations are in line with those of softwood and confirm the CML as the most sensitive part in the anatomical structure of the hardwoods that is altered by the treatments. The changes in CML of poplar are shown in [Figure 5](#) where the presence of micro checks are apparent in the transverse section when untreated ([Figure 5a](#)) and MW treated poplar wood ([Figure 5b, d, f](#)) are compared. Micro checks were created along the CML between the fibres shown in TLSs ([Figure 5e, g](#)) while no checks were observed in the untreated samples ([Figure 5c](#))

Figure 5. SEM images of untreated poplar control sample (a, c) and apparent checks in TS of MW treated poplar wood (b, d, f). Micro checks along the CML between the fibres shown in TLSs (e, g) while no checks were observed in the untreated samples (c).

The observed effect of TM on beech wood cell walls was found similar to that in Scots pine (Figure 6). The introduced buckling and indentations in the CML between the thick-walled beech fibres (Figure 6b, c) are similar to these observed in Scots pine (Figure 6d, e).

Figure 6. Comparison between buckling and indentations in the CML of beech (a, b, c) and Scots pine (d, e).

The conclusions of the study on microstructural changes caused by microwave and thermal modification are summarised as:

- Examination using SEM of the structural effects of TM and MW treatments on two softwoods (spruce, Scots pine) and two hardwoods (poplar, beech) showed a variety of ultra- and microstructural changes within the wood structure.
- Observations showed variations between both wood type and wood species.
- A unifying structural morphological modification observed for all four wood species and the two treatments (MW and TM) were changes in the compound middle lamella (CML) and outer secondary cell wall regions. Effects observed included buckling, cracking and development of indentations (holes) in the CML and closely associated (cell layers) regions. The effects were most pronounced in spruce and beech with TM and MW treatments.
- The micro- and ultrastructural changes produced in the wood through the TM and MW treatments applied are consistent with the enhanced uptake of the bioPCM recorded in Deliverable 2.1.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Impregnation of wood and leaching of ethyl palmitate

Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) sapwood was selected for the modelling study. Scots pine sapwood is a potential candidate to serve as a middle lamella core in 3-layer parquet with integrated bioPCM, which justifies the selection. The selected species was described in detail in Deliverable 2.1. The impregnation technology has been shown and discussed in detail in Deliverable 2.2. Identical impregnation method was used in the present study. Wood lamellae with dimensions of 10 × 25 × 470 mm were conditioned in a room climate to 5-7% MC prior to the impregnation. The lamellae were weighed, wood density calculated and lamellae grouped in ascending order by the density. Twenty-seven (27) lamellae were selected by taking samples with an even step along the scale of density, from the lowest to the highest density for each of the impregnation tests. This guarantees that the lamellae in a test comprise the whole density range while the average densities of the tests are similar (Table 2), i.e., the selection ensures that the tests are comparable regarding the wood density, which is an important factor in wood impregnation.

Table 2. Average density of Scots pine lamellae in the impregnation tests ($n = 27$ per test). Standard deviations in parentheses.

Pressure, bar	Duration of impregnation pressure, min		
	15	30	45
3	572.8 (43.8)	574.7 (46.3)	575.4 (43.0)
6	576.3 (41.9)	572.8 (43.1)	571.7 (43.5)
9	568.5 (32.1)	567.7 (38.7)	572.4 (42.9)

Prior to the impregnation, the lamellae were weighed and placed in an autoclave. Ethyl palmitate (EP) was used as a bioPCM for impregnation in the wood. The EP was melted at 70°C prior to impregnation.

Nine impregnation schedules with pressure and duration as variables were applied to study the effect of schedule parameters on the retention of the EP in the wood and its leaching. The aimed impregnation was full-cell impregnation, involving vacuum and pressure to fill the wood cell walls and lumens with the impregnation liquid. The impregnation schedule used to impregnate EP in the lamellae is shown schematically in Figure 7. It is the impregnation schedule recommended in Deliverable 2.2.

Figure 7. Schematic illustration of the tested impregnation schedules for wood lamellae with ethyl palmitate. The yellow part of the illustration indicates the presence of liquid in the autoclave.

The pressure step of the impregnation is the most active and influential part of the technology that contributes to the uptake of PCM and thus, it was selected as variable in terms of pressure (3 levels of 3, 6 and 9 bars) and durations of 15, 30 and 60 min. The other steps of the schedule were kept constant as shown in Figure 7. For each experimental impregnation, 27 samples (lamellae) were selected and tested. Data analysis was performed using Minitab 18 statistical software.

Leaching of the EP from the lamellae was carried out identically to the test protocol described in Deliverable 2.1. The impregnated samples (lamellae) were weighed and placed in a climate chamber with a cycling temperature between 5-45°C. The temperature decreased to 5°C with a rate of 1°C/min and an isotherm course at 5°C for 5 h was maintained. After the cooling stage, the temperature increased to 45°C with a rate of 1°C/min following another isotherm course at 45°C for 5 h. The process was repeated 10 times, i.e., the samples experienced 10 cycles of cooling at 5°C and heating at 45°C. After the end of the process, the samples were weighed, and the leaching was calculated as a difference between the initial and final weight of the sample related to the initial weight and expressed in percentage, i.e., the weight percentage gain.

Impregnation of wood sawdust and particles with ethyl palmitate was carried out identically to the method described in Deliverable 2.1. EP was melted in an oven at 70°C prior to impregnation. The impregnation started with initial heating of wood particles in the EP for 60 min. Initial vacuum of 100 mbar was applied for 10 min to the material aiming at evacuation of the air. The EP was pressurized at 8 bars for 10 min. The wood sawdust and particles were taken out of EP, left to drain and weighed to calculate the WPG of EP. The impregnated wood particles were placed in a funnel immediately after the impregnation and left to drain the surplus of EP in an oven at 50°C for 24 h.

4. Modelling of solid wood impregnation with bioPCM

Modelling of liquid transport in wood allows researchers to predict impregnation depth, rate, and uniformity under varying parameters of the impregnation process, e.g., the depth of vacuum, pressure rate, centrifugal or pulsed forces). Modern models and finite-element simulations possess good prediction, can optimize the processing conditions and improve the impregnation efficiency to achieve uniformity of fluid distribution in the modelled wood materials.

A vast majority of the transport models are dedicated to water/water solutions in wood. Water is naturally presented in the material and is also interest during wood processing, e.g., wood drying, impregnation of solid wood for protection purpose, impregnation of wood chips in pulping.

A simplified model for dried wood with lumen impregnation has been developed, where V and ρ denote the volume and density, respectively (Wu *et al.* 2017). This model helps in understanding the process of wood impregnation and its effects on the wood structure. Additionally, linear regression models have been used to study the relationship between equilibrium moisture content (EMC) and weight percent gain (WPG) in wood

impregnation processes (Pařil 2016). These models show a statistically significant dependence between these two factors, indicating that higher WPG correlates with changes in moisture content. These models aim to predict and optimize the impregnation process, considering the complex interactions between the wood structure, impregnating agents, and treatment conditions. Important parameters used in the impregnation models are permeability coefficient (k), liquid viscosity (μ), pressure gradient (∇P), wood porosity (ϕ), capillary radius and its distribution, diffusion coefficient and contact angle at the liquid-solid phase.

4.1 Ethyl palmitate as impregnation liquid

Properties of ethyl palmitate (EP) as a liquid of interest in the project are as important for the process result as the properties of wood and impregnation parameters. Ethyl palmitate may not form significant covalent bonds with lignin or other wood components. Instead, it is retained within the wood structure through physical interactions. The main properties of EP have been shown and discussed extensively in Deliverable 2.2. While water penetrates the wood cell wall, interacting with the hydroxyl groups and causing volumetric swelling of the material of ca. 16% after 96 h, the volumetric swelling of samples in EP was negligible and less than 0.5% and thus, demonstrating no penetration and interaction with the wood cell wall polymers. This led to the conclusion that EP must be forced into wood by external force, i.e. impregnated by vacuum-pressure process. The non-polar nature of EP, lack of interaction to the wood constituents and leaching are important properties that must be considered in the impregnation model.

According to literature, there is a scarcity of data and modelling approaches for impregnation of porous media with phase change materials. *No data was found on modelling the impregnation of ethyl palmitate in solid wood.* Before approaching the topic, several key considerations, including the chemical interactions between the ethyl palmitate and wood components, the physical structure of the wood, and the environmental conditions affecting the process must be taken in account. Here are the basics to be considered.

1. Type of impregnation agents (e.g., water, oils, waxes and resins, monomers vs. polymers) and chemical interactions with the substrate. Ethyl palmitate, a fatty acid ester, interacts with wood components through complex mechanisms. Unlike free fatty acids, esters like ethyl palmitate may have different reactivity profiles. An example is lignin, the most hydrophobic polymer in wood, that can influence the oxidation process (Alireza, 2012). However, unlike free fatty acids, ethyl palmitate may not be significantly affected by lignin in terms of oxidation rate. Instead, *lignin might affect the diffusion and retention of ethyl palmitate within the wood matrix.* Wood carbohydrates (cellulose and hemicellulose) generally increase the rate of oxidation of fatty acids, but their effect on esters like ethyl palmitate may be less pronounced. These carbohydrates can still act as catalysts or influence the microenvironment where the ester interacts with wood.

2. Wood species, structure and permeability

The heterogeneous and porous nature of wood significantly affects the impregnation process. The cellular structure and porosity of wood influence the retention and distribution of ethyl palmitate within the wood matrix. Different wood species (hardwood vs. softwood) have varying densities and compositions, which influences the impregnation and retention of ethyl palmitate. For example, Scots pine sapwood, with its lower density, might allow faster penetration compared to denser hardwoods like beech (Deliverable 2.1 and 2.2).

3. Impregnation methods and parameters.

Temperature of impregnation and wood moisture content are also important factors that affect the impregnation and stability of ethyl palmitate in wood. Higher temperature decreases the viscosity of ethyl palmitate, while wood moisture content can affect the retention of liquid.

4. Impregnation uptake, weight percent gain, leaching, oxidation and stability of the agent

While ethyl palmitate is less reactive than polyunsaturated fatty acids like linoleic acid, it can still undergo oxidation, albeit at a slower rate. The oxidation process of ethyl palmitate on wood surfaces may follow a less complex free radical mechanism compared to free fatty acids. However, the presence of wood constituents can still influence this process, with lignin potentially retarding oxidation and carbohydrates having a minimal catalytic effect (Alireza 2012). Another aspect of impregnation with PCM to be considered are the changes in wood properties, especially dimensional stability and material mechanical properties.

5. Analytical methods

Depending on the study's objectives, analytical techniques such as Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) can be employed to reveal the interactions between ethyl palmitate and wood components.

4.2 Modelling principles

Modelling wood impregnation involves simulating how liquids move into the porous structure of wood using physical laws of fluid flow and diffusion. Several mathematical and computational approaches have been developed to capture the complexity of the process, depending on wood type, impregnation medium, and process conditions. Most models are based on Darcy's law, which relates volumetric flow rate to pressure gradient, pore structure, and fluid viscosity. In centrifugal or vacuum-pressure impregnation scenarios, the liquid flow is described by adaptations of Darcy's law that account for radial or longitudinal flow through the anisotropic wood network. The porosity and permeability of the wood are key parameters. These can vary between earlywood and latewood and depend on wood cell orientation. Capillary flow is dominant in early stages, particularly in tracheids or vessels, while diffusion becomes important at later stages for cell-wall bound water. Based on literature data, several types of models and approaches are distinguished.

Microscopy and hydrodynamic models treat the wood as a continuum porous medium described by Darcy's or Washburn's equations. The Washburn model is often applied for one-dimensional flow behaviour in softwoods (Perre *et al.* 2022). The authors use Washburn-based approach applying X-ray computer tomography for prediction of imbibition dynamics of water and silicone oil in soft- and hardwood porous media. This was the first approach for modelling of solid wood impregnation in the project.

Statistical-wood models combine micro-CT data and statistical pore structure analysis to predict time- and impregnation parameter-dependent uptake with high accuracy (Burridge *et al.* 2019). Statistical modelling was the second approach for modelling the impregnation of solid wood with ethyl palmitate.

Another modelling approach is *finite-element and computational fluid dynamics* (CFD) models, which are used for simulating pressure-driven impregnation, including effects of anisotropy and heterogeneous pore size distribution (Evysdotter *et al.* 2025). This approach was used to model the impregnation of a single fibre with ethyl palmitate.

There are also advanced and specialized models include models of piezo periodic fields, using pulsed pressure waves and liquid-pore interaction dynamics to accelerate impregnation, achieving high penetration depth within seconds (Kunitzkaya *et al.* 2018). Microstructural models represent wood as an assembly of capillaries or "spherical elements" interacting as a fluid-solid network to simulate end-grain impregnation geometrically (Shamaev 2020). Data on phase change material (PCM) impregnation models, coupling heat and mass transport simulations for wood's thermal enhancement performance are scarce with few references found, e.g., Hartig *et al.* 2023 and Grzybek *et al.* 2023.

4.3 Washburn equation-based modelling of flow in porous systems

The filling behaviour in porous media has been investigated since the beginning of the 20th century. It was first studied in 1905 by Bell and Cameron (1905), and subsequently by Lucas (1918) and Washburn (1921). Their main finding, today known widely as Washburn's law or Lucas-Washburn (LW) equation, predicts how the penetration length of the liquid imbibition front in a uniform porous medium grows as a function of time,

$$l(t) = Kt^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Washburn's law reflects the balance between the sum of external pressure and surface tension, which drives the flow, and viscous friction, which resists it. These opposing forces are present in all situations involving imbibition, with specific details, such as the structure of the porous medium and the material properties of the invading liquid, appearing in the proportionality constant K . The result of this balance leads to the slowing-down dynamics of the front, captured by the diffusive-like exponent, $n = 1/2$, in (1). Many practical processes rely on Washburn's law: it is used to characterize the wettability of food powders (Wangler and Kohlus 2018) and the porosity of construction materials (Lee *et al.* 2018), to model pore-scale dynamics in oil recovery (Gruener and Huber 2019) and paper micro-fluidics (Tabeling 2014), and even to assess the permeability of seeds (Louf *et al.* 2018) and soils (Truong *et al.* 2015) and in the agriculture (Zhang *et al.* 2021) Washburn's law is currently used to determine the pore size distribution in wood by mercury intrusion porosimetry. The model has been

constantly modified and extended, e.g., to non-uniform (Chassagne *et al.* 2019) and non-circular (Yu *et al.* 2018) cross section of the capillary tube but it is still widely applied (e.g., Cai *et al.* 2021, July 2011) and theoretically accredited (e.g., Ruiz-Gutiérrez *et al.* 2022, Rapajić *et al.* 2025) paying particular attention to the important role of the slip coefficient (e.g., Rapajić *et al.* 2025, July 2011) to simulate realistic conditions of imbibition.

4.3.1 Single capillary tube modelling

Figure 8. Single capillary tube AB with uniform internal circular cross section with radius r to illustrate the basics Washburn theory (illustration from Washburn 1921).

The classical Washburn’s formulation refers to the scheme in [Figure 8](#) and shares a similar dynamic mechanism with capillary flow in hollow tubes assuming the validity of the main hypotheses of Poiseuille’s law. Such assumptions are that the fluid is incompressible and Newtonian, the flow is laminar through a pipe of constant circular cross-section that is substantially longer than its diameter, and there is no acceleration of fluid in the pipe. This provides the following law for the liquid penetration under given pressure inside a single capillary tube of uniform internal circular cross section throughout, the radius being r (Washburn 1921)

$$\frac{dl}{dt} = \frac{\left[P_A + g \cdot D(h - l_s \sin \psi) + \frac{2\gamma}{r} \cos \theta \right] (r^2 + 4\epsilon r)}{8\eta l}$$

where l is the length of the liquid column in the capillary at the time t , D is the density, γ is the surface tension and η is the viscosity of the liquid, θ is the solid-liquid angle of contact and ϵ is the slip coefficient. The latter accounts for fluid-solid slippage to more accurately model fluids that do not adhere to a no-slip boundary as in ideal laminar flow, making the model valid for a wider range of conditions and materials.

Assuming $\psi=0$ (horizontal capillary tube), integration of above differential equation provides:

$$l^2 = \frac{\left(P_A + D \cdot g \cdot h + \frac{2\gamma}{r} \cos \theta \right) (r^2 + 4\epsilon r) t}{4\eta}$$

where ϵ and θ being in general functions of t (Washburn 1921).

Then, indicating $P_E = P_A + D g h$ the overall external driving pressure on the liquid, the corresponding penetrated volume in a single tube of radius r at the time t can be written as:

$$V_r = \pi \cdot r^2 \cdot l = \frac{\pi}{2} r^2 \left(P_E + \frac{2\gamma}{r} \cos \theta \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (r^2 + 4\epsilon r)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

4.3.2 Porous body modelling

For calculation purposes, Washburn assumed that the penetration of the pores of a body by a liquid in which it is immersed may be taken as equivalent to the penetration of n cylindrical capillary tubes of radii r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n . Therefore, the liquid that enters the pores of the body at the end of the time t can be calculated as:

$$V = \sum_1^n V_{r_i} = \frac{\pi}{2} \left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{i=1}^n r_i^2 \left(P_E + \frac{2\gamma}{r_i} \cos \theta \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (r_i^2 + 4\epsilon r_i)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

4.3.3 Model adaptation to ethyl palmitate (EP) impregnation of wood structure

The application of the W macroscopic model to wood impregnation by bioPCM implicitly assumes the liquid entering in wood is mainly due to bulk flow through the lumens of the wood cells without noticeable diffusion through the wood cell wall or chemical interactions with its polymers. Output reported in the Deliverable D2.2 confirms as valid, overall, such an assumption.

On the other hand, results obtained from the experiments of impregnation with ethyl palmitate carried out at three different times and different pressures agree, overall, with the general law (1) of the model by which the entered volume at a given pressure, liquid properties and impregnation conditions are linearly dependent from the square root of the time (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Experimental data of ethyl palmitate (EP) impregnated volumes at 3 and 6 bars pressure after three durations (times).

As reported in the Deliverable D2.1, the 3D image analysis of the wood structure reconstructed by means of the X-ray micro-CT allows the measurement of the wood pore size distribution:

$$V_{d_i} = f(d_i) \quad (4)$$

where $f(d_i)$ is the pore volume fraction exhibiting average diameter d_i being the pore space inside the imaged wood sample partitioned in n pore size classes having width equal to the double of the image voxel size ($3.25 \times 2 = 6.5 \mu\text{m}$).

Therefore, application of the W equation for wood impregnation with EP could be done, in principle, if the slip coefficient ε and contact angle θ would be known as functions of t after a slight modification of the equation (3). Namely, substituting r_i with $d/2$ and introducing hypothesis that the penetration process in wood starts by filling the larger pore space fractions first, then the smaller ones and thus, equation (3) can be written as:

$$V_d = \frac{\pi}{16} \left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=d_{max}}^{i=d_{min}} d_i^2 \cdot \sqrt{\left(P_E + \frac{4\gamma}{d_i} \cos\vartheta\right) \cdot (d_i^2 + 8 \cdot \varepsilon(t) \cdot d_i)} \quad (5)$$

where d_{max} and d_{min} are the maximum and minimum pore diameter classes found in the wood structure and d is the diameter corresponding to the penetrated volume V_d (as calculated with equation (5) according to pore size distribution (4).

4.3.4 Model calibration

The remaining unknown parameters $\varepsilon(P, t)$ and θ can be determined by calibrating the final model (5) using known results of penetrated volume from experimental data obtained at different pressures and times.

Inverse numerical solution of equation (5) using experimental values of V , P and t at any fixed value θ proved that the slip coefficient values ε fit very well with the exponential function: $\varepsilon(t) = a \cdot \exp(-b \cdot t)$ at any pressure, as shown in the example in Figure 10.

Slip coefficient (W model)

Figure 10. Slip coefficient functions calibration. Example of fitting of the ε values obtained from the modified Washburn model (5) applied to Scots pine wood using experimental values of ethyl palmitate (EP) penetrated volume, pressure and time.

Then, $\varepsilon(t)$ functions at pressure different from those used for calibration can be determined by linear interpolation of the parameters a and b of the exponential function.

The use of the apparent slip coefficient functions obtained from the above calibration process allows more accurate predictions from the model (5) and, in practice, incorporates a more dynamic model of the fluid-solid interaction than using a static contact angle model of the fluid-solid interaction.

On the other hand, numerical solution of equation (5) obtained by fixing ε values, provided the model was very low sensitive to the θ values, that is according to our modified Washburn model the apparent contact angle between ethyl palmitate and wood cell walls has a neglectable role in the penetration process and can be

obtained arbitrary. The above approach does not influence significantly the predicted results of the retention (WPG) at a given time.

4.3.5 Example of application of the modified Washburn equation and model verification

In Figure 11 we provide as two possible examples of application of our modified Washburn model the predicted theoretical times needed for the complete impregnation of the whole pore volume of Scots pine sapwood and the weights (volumes × 0.86) penetrated at various pressures of the impregnation process.

Figure 11. Example of outputs of the Washburn based model applied to the impregnation process of ethyl palmitate in Scots pine sapwood.

The size of the completely filled pores provided by the model after ten minutes of impregnation ranged from 28.2 microns at 2 bars till 17.4 microns at 8 bars. The measured retention of ethyl palmitate in the 9 impregnations was used for model verification. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison between measured and predicted retention of EP (data from 10 impregnations, n = 253).

Pressure, bar	Duration, min	Measured retention, kg/m ³	Predicted retention, kg/m ³	Difference, kg/m ³	Difference, %
3	15	203	315	112	55.2
3	30	384	378	6	1.6
3	45	399	402	3	0.8
6	15	406	411	5	1.2
6	30	425	439	14	3.3
6*	30	431	439	7	1.6
6	45	445	451	6	1.3
9	15	447	459	12	2.7
9	30	437	465	28	6.4
9	45	442	496	54	12.2

*Data from an impregnation schedule in Deliverable 2.2

The differences between measured and predicted retention values are small, with an exception for impregnation at 3 bars and 15 min. The two groups were compared by ANOVA's Tukey's test with no significant difference found. The model is applicable to wood treated by microwave and thermal modification; data on the treated wood porosity measured by X-CT is available in the program. An example of the model application programming interface, presenting a set of rules and protocols that allows the software applications and components to communicate and exchange data is shown in **Appendix**.

4.4 Statistical modelling

The model that should be developed must serve practical purposes to allow a quick estimation of the optimal amount of PCM in the wood and the thermal response of the impregnated wood. Statistical modelling was selected as an additional approach due to its simplicity, complexity and the ability of the model to estimate large number of samples, i.e., the entire batch of solid wood lamellae for impregnation. It is also easily applicable in industrial conditions to predict and assess the uptake of PCM in the wood.

Experimental validation of wood impregnation simulations typically involves quantifying how well modelled predictions (e.g., uptake, penetration depth, spatial distribution) match real experimental outcomes. These tests require both mass-based and microscopic characterization methods to evaluate impregnation uniformity, kinetics, and pore filling behaviour across different scales. The two modelling approaches in Deliverable 2.3 comprise the measurements and calculations listed below.

1. Gravimetric and density-based calculations

Changes in material's density provide a macroscopic overview of impregnation uniformity. The density before and after treatment is used to compute the volume fraction of void space occupied by the impregnant. This is also effective for comparing results to simulation models using Washburn law approach. Wood moisture content (MC) is of minor importance and is neglected.

2. Mass uptake and retention measurements

The simplest method involves measuring the mass gain of wood samples before and after impregnation. This allows validation of modelled impregnation rates and saturation limits. For example, during PCM impregnation tests under vacuum-pressure cycles (0.3-0.6-0.9 MPa at 70°C), the difference in mass corresponds directly to PCM uptake and impregnation efficiency. The theoretical maximum uptake can be computed using known PCM density and compared to measured impregnation values to assess error margins.

3. Microscopy and imaging-based validation

Light and scanning microscopy (LM and SEM) allow optical sectioning of transverse or longitudinal wood sections to reveal the changes in the cell lumen and walls. X-ray computer tomography (X-ray CT) enables high-resolution 3D mapping of pore filling and impregnation fronts inside wood specimens, without destructive sectioning. Quantification of filled vs. unfilled pores, total porosity, and spatial uniformity can be directly compared to numerical model predictions for impregnation depth and anisotropic penetration patterns. CT imaging can segment filled pores by X-ray density and compute filled pore ratios.

4. Thermal validation of PCM-impregnated wood

After impregnation, T-tests verify predicted enhancements in heat storage capacity based on modelled PCM distribution and loading level. Overall, combining macroscopic gravimetric validation with X-ray CT imaging yields a robust framework for verifying impregnation models to confirm both the total uptake of liquid and 3D infiltration distribution patterns.

4.4.1 Treatment and wood density effects on the weight percentage gains of the bioPCM

Wood density of Scots pine sapwood lamellae varies widely from 430 to 700 kg/m³. Plotting the wood density and the weight percentage gain ([Figure 12](#)) showed that there is a linear relationship between the two parameters for Scots pine sapwood samples and beech. This is valid for untreated and thermally modified wood. Spruce wood treated by microwave and thermal modification demonstrated no relationship between density and weight percentage gain. The above shows the effect of wood anatomy on the impregnability of the wood species – while pine sapwood and beech are permeable, spruce is refractory wood species with limited impregnability. Characteristics and analysis of the wood species and their permeability have been performed in Deliverable 2.1. Deliverable 2.2 recommended Scots pine sapwood and spruce for tests in industrial scale.

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Thus, a statistical model for Scots pine sapwood can be a valuable tool for control of the impregnation retention and give an indication about the expected latent heat of the impregnated wood with bioPCM.

Figure 12. Relationship between wood density and weight percentage gain in microwave and thermally modified spruce, Scots pine sapwood and beech impregnated with ethyl palmitate.

The used model is a two-factor analysis of variance including time and pressure as factors and density of wood as a covariate. Interaction between all factors and covariates are included. It is found by the model that there are significant interaction effects between pressure and density of wood, as well as time and density of wood. Mean values and relationship between wood density and weight percentage gain of Scots pine sapwood impregnated by the 9 schedules are demonstrated in Table 4 and Figure 13. The first number shows the impregnation time, the second is the applied pressure. The grey areas in the graph represent the confidence intervals of the variable weight percentage gain. Some of the other groups have flatter slopes, the group of 3 bars and 15 min differs significantly, i.e., the slope is almost parallel to the density axis.

Table 4. Mean values of weight percentage gain (%) and retention (kg/m³) achieved in the 9 tests (*n* = 27 in each test). Standard deviations within parentheses.

Duration	Pressure 3 bars		Pressure 6 bars		Pressure 9 bars	
	WPG, %	Retention, kg/m ³	WPG, %	Retention, kg/m ³	WPG, %	Retention, kg/m ³
15 min	35.5 (7.8)	203.3 (47.2)	71.0 (10.1)	406.0 (40.0)	76.5 (11.0)	433.6 (37.0)
30 min	67.0 (9.2)	383.6 (47.6)	75.0 (10.7)	425.4 (32.7)	77.4 (9.3)	436.8 (30.1)
45 min	69.8 (8.7)	399.3 (39.8)	78.6 (11.5)	445.0 (37.4)	77.8 (9.1)	441.7 (28.9)

Figure 13. Relationship between wood density (kg/m³) and weight percentage gain (%) of Scots pine sapwood impregnated by 9 impregnation schedules.

Apparently, pressure of 3 bars for 15 min does not ensure significant penetration of EP in the wood lamellae. The uptake of bioPCM is improved significantly at 3 bar and 30 min impregnation (the green line). The significance of the factors is listed below.

Response: **Weight percentage gain (%)**

	Sum Sq	Df	F value	Pr(>F)	
Time	9164.6	2	114.3566	< 2.2e-16	***
Pressure	17953.9	2	224.0311	< 2.2e-16	***
Wood density	10848.4	1	270.7342	< 2.2e-16	***
Time:Pressure	11270.2	4	70.3157	< 2.2e-16	***
Time:Wood density	284.7	2	3.5525	0.03027	*
Pressure:Wood density	1973.7	2	24.6279	2.128e-10	***
Time:Pressure:Wood density	237.8	4	1.4838	0.20796	
Residuals	9015.8	225			

To understand the effect of the above factors on the WPG, the slopes of the lines were examined, i.e. the relationship to density of wood, as also illustrated in Figure 13. Analysing the three studied pressures, it was found only one significant different slope for pressure of 3 bars and pressure time of 15 min where the slope is less steep compared to the same pressure but for 45 min. For other two pressures of 6 and 9 bars no differences were observed, i.e., within the pressures of 6 and 9 bars, the three durations of the process did not lead to different result regarding the weight percentage gain.

Pressure = 3 bar:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
time15 - time30	0.07413	0.0390	225	1.899	0.1414
time15 - time45	0.12563	0.0405	225	3.104	0.0061 *
time30 - time45	0.05149	0.0394	225	1.307	0.3928

Pressure = 6 bar:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
time15 - time30	0.04907	0.0414	225	1.186	0.4629
time15 - time45	0.06120	0.0411	225	1.488	0.2988
time30 - time45	0.01213	0.0406	225	0.299	0.9519

Pressure = 9 bar:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
time15 - time30	-0.03593	0.0432	225	-0.831	0.6840
time15 - time45	-0.00163	0.0451	225	-0.036	0.9993
time30 - time45	0.03430	0.0472	225	0.727	0.7477

The three groups of time were analysed identically. When impregnation time of 15 min was considered, there was a significant difference in relation to density of wood between pressure 3 and 6 bars as well as for pressure of 3 and 9 bars. Similar results were observed for time of 30 and 45 min (one exception in the group of 45 min where pressure 3 vs 6 bars was significant and pressure 3 vs 9 bars almost).

Time = 15 min:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
pressure3 - pressure6	0.16827	0.0410	225	4.099	0.0002 ***
pressure3 - pressure9	0.22234	0.0405	225	5.485	<.0001 ***
pressure6 - pressure9	0.05407	0.0414	225	1.305	0.3939

Time = 30 min:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
pressure3 - pressure6	0.14320	0.0394	225	3.634	0.0010 ***
pressure3 - pressure9	0.11228	0.0418	225	2.684	0.0212 **
pressure6 - pressure9	-0.03092	0.0432	225	-0.716	0.7540

Time = 45 min:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
pressure3 - pressure6	0.10384	0.0406	225	2.560	0.0298 **
pressure3 - pressure9	0.09509	0.0450	225	2.111	0.0898 *
pressure6 - pressure9	-0.00876	0.0448	225	-0.195	0.9792

As an example, the three slopes for time of 45 min are plotted in Figure 14. The three slopes are negative, but for pressure 3 the slope is less steep. The slopes of 6 and 9 bars pressure are similar, and both are significant against the slope of 3 bar pressure.

The interpretation of the results shows that, despite the application time, pressure of 3 bars is not enough to achieve high weight percentage gain and should be omitted. On the other hand, the pressures of 6 and 9 bars ensure similar WPGs with no statistically significant differences. It can be recommended 6 bars pressure to be used for impregnation of the lamellae, which ensures easier, faster and more economic impregnation process compared to 9 bars. Within the three studied times (15, 30 and 45 min), no significant difference was found regarding the WPG when 6 bars pressure is applied. The above findings are in line with the empirical conclusions in Deliverable 2.2 where 6 bars pressure and 30 min impregnation time were recommended.

Figure 14. Significance and similarity of the slopes 45:6 and 45:9 when compared to slope 45:3.

To compare the results for pressure and time factors better, they can be compared at different values for wood density. At a wood density level of 500 kg/m³, the following differences in overall weight gain percentage were observed. If pressure 3 is applied there are differences in weight gain percentages compared to other pressures. This is observed for the three impregnation times and is apparently visible in Figure 13 (in the left part) where

the lines start on a lower level (i.e., lower weight gain percentage). Pressure 6 combined with time of 15 min is also slightly lower than other groups (compare to pressure of 6 bars and longer times or with pressure of 9 bars).

At a wood density level of 650 kg/m³, there is still difference in the group of 3 bars pressure and 15 min, but all other groups demonstrate comparable weight percentage gains (ca. 60%, see Figure 13 in the right part); all lines end on similar WPG levels except the one for 3 bars and 15 min.

There are two possibilities to illustrate means/boxplots for the impregnations at wood density of 500 and 650 kg/m³. It must be noted that the results look slightly different from each other as the first plots illustrate modelled means at a specific wood density (Figure 15), while the other plots are descriptive statistics of the test data (Figure 16).

Figure 15. Modelled average values of the weight percentage gain estimated by the model for wood density of 500 kg/m³ (upper graph) and 650 kg/m³ (lower graph).

Figure 16. Selecting data from the dataset where the observations of wood density lower than 550 kg/m³ (upper graph) and higher than 600 kg/m³ (lower graph) are summarised.

4.4.2 Treatment and wood density effects on leaching of the bioPCM and model verification

Wood density has no significant effect on ethyl palmitate leaching. When the leaching of ethyl palmitate (in %) is plotted against the density, the relationship between the two was not strong for most of the treatment groups. The level of leaching generally is highest for the treatment of 9 bars pressure and duration of 45 min and lowest for 3 bars pressure for 15 min. As seen in the plot, (Figure 17) the slopes (relation to density of wood is very similar for all groups.

Figure 17. Relationship between wood density (kg/m³) and leaching (%) of ethyl palmitate from Scots pine sapwood impregnated by 9 impregnation schedules.

From the model it was found that there are significant interaction effects between the pressure and time.

Response: **Leaching (%)**

	Sum Sq	Df	F value	Pr(>F)	
Time	582.06	2	32.6206	3.632e-13	***
Pressure	1403.74	2	78.6704	< 2.2e-16	***
Wood density	19.12	1	2.1426	0.1447	
Time:pressure	290.79	4	8.1485	3.742e-06	***
Time:wood density	31.08	2	1.7418	0.1776	
Pressure:wood density	32.90	2	1.8438	0.1606	
Time:pressure:wood density	33.28	4	0.9327	0.4457	

However, analysing the three studied pressures, no significantly different slopes were found within the pressure groups. The same was valid for the three groups of time. Since there are no clear relations of the leaching to wood density and the line slopes are similar, the wood density was removed from the model for an easier comparison.

Figure 18. Summary statistics by bar charts showing average values and deviations of leaching grouped by the three test durations.

The analysis below and **Figure 19** showed that there were significant differences in leaching between the pressure groups within the same time except at time of 30 min where the pressure of 6 and 9 bars did not differ significantly.

Time = 15 min:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
pressure3 - pressure6	-2.32	0.819	234	-2.827	0.0141 **
pressure3 - pressure9	-7.79	0.819	234	-9.504	<.0001 ***
pressure6 - pressure9	-5.47	0.819	234	-6.677	<.0001 ***

Time = 30 min:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
pressure3 - pressure6	-5.07	0.819	234	-6.192	<.0001 ***
pressure3 - pressure9	-4.03	0.819	234	-4.923	<.0001 ***
pressure6 - pressure9	1.04	0.819	234	1.269	0.4141

Time = 45 min:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
pressure3 - pressure6	-2.49	0.819	234	-3.037	0.0075 ***
pressure3 - pressure9	-5.67	0.819	234	-6.923	<.0001 ***
pressure6 - pressure9	-3.18	0.819	234	-3.886	0.0004 ***

When the time groups are replaced by the three pressures, the leaching is compared at the same pressure. Using a pressure of 3 and 6 bars and a time of 15 min leads to a lower leaching percentage compared to time 30 or 45 min. When pressure of 9 bars is used for 45 min, the leaching is significantly different from the other times.

Figure 19. Summary statistics by bar charts showing average values and deviations of leaching grouped by the three test pressures.

Pressure = 3 bar:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
time15 - time30	-3.185	0.819	234	-3.887	0.0004 ***
time15 - time45	-4.251	0.819	234	-5.188	<.0001 ***
time30 - time45	-1.067	0.819	234	-1.302	0.3957

Pressure = 6 bar:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
time15 - time30	-5.942	0.819	234	-7.252	<.0001 ***
time15 - time45	-4.423	0.819	234	-5.398	<.0001 ***

time30 - time45 1.519 0.819 234 1.854 0.1547

Pressure = 9 bar:

contrast	estimate	SE	df	t.ratio	p.value
time15 - time30	0.569	0.819	234	0.694	0.7671
time15 - time45	-2.136	0.819	234	-2.607	0.0262 **
time30 - time45	-2.705	0.819	234	-3.301	0.0032 **

When the model considers only wood density lower than 500 kg/m³, the mean values of leaching below are calculated. Negative leaching means for pressure of 3 bars were calculated while the leaching is positive when pressure of 6 or 9 bars has been applied. The physical meaning of the negative values is moisture adsorption of the lamellae during the process of leaching that leads to higher weight than that before the leaching and thus, a negative value is calculated. At wood density of 650 kg/m³ and higher, an identical pattern was found when the significant differences in leaching were observed again between the pressure of 3 bars and both higher pressures and times.

Time	Pressure	Mean	SE	df	Lower.CL	Upper.CL
15	3	-3.469	1.13	225	-5.699	-1.238
30	3	-1.960	1.11	225	-4.139	0.220
45	3	-1.450	1.18	225	-3.770	0.869
15	6	0.327	1.21	225	-2.063	2.716
30	6	4.157	1.15	225	1.898	6.415
45	6	2.854	1.12	225	0.641	5.066
15	9	2.909	1.14	225	0.655	5.163
30	9	3.831	1.18	225	1.514	6.148
45	9	4.342	1.30	225	1.789	6.895

Pressure of 3 bars ensures the lowest leaching. However, when the WPG is considered, the impregnation schedule of 3 bars pressure was rejected because of too low WPG. Wood impregnated at 6 and 9 bars has no statistical difference in leaching of the impregnated PCM. Thus, it can be concluded that pressure of 6 bars for 30 min serves best the intent to achieve high WPG with low leaching. Ethyl palmitate in non-polar liquid when melted and does not undergo interaction with the wood polymers. It is concluded that leaching of ethyl palmitate from the wood lamellae cannot be eliminated but only restricted to the few percent measured after impregnation and leaching and showed already.

With exceptions of the lines for 3 bars pressure and the three times and the line for 6 bars at 15 min, the rest of the regression lines in [Figure 13](#) are similar and can be described by the equation $WPG = -0.223 \times density + 202.69$ (the one for pressure 6 bars and 30 min duration). In order to verify the model, WPG data from the control impregnation of Scots pine solid wood lamellae with the impregnation schedule of 6 bars pressure and 30 min duration in Deliverable 2.2 were calculated ([Table 5](#)) according to the above equation.

Table 5. Wood density, measured and calculated WPG in Scots pine sapwood lamellae. Mean values in the blue field.

Wood density, kg/m ³	WPG measured, %	WPG calculated, %
668.1	51.8	53.7
501.3	77.4	90.9
668.9	55.0	53.5
531.9	86.1	84.1
611.9	75.0	66.2
510.6	97.2	88.8
537.9	85.8	82.7
543.8	85.1	81.4
594.9	72.7	70.0
570.2	77.0	75.5
574.0	76.3	74.7

The results are plotted in [Figure 20](#). The model explains ca. 80% of the weight percentage gain in Scots pine sapwood lamellae. Additionally, the calculated and measured values were compared by ANOVA's Tukey's test to find no significant difference between the groups.

Figure 20. Verification of the model applied to an impregnation schedule with 10 lamellae in Deliverable 2.2.

Thermal verification. The verified Washburn and statistical models are useful tools to predict the amount of bioPCM in the wood structure. One step further is to predict the latent enthalpy of the system wood-bioPCM. The prediction must consider that the measured enthalpy of a wood-bioPCM composite does not necessarily results in the sum of wood's sensible enthalpy and bioPCM's latent enthalpy proportional to their mass fractions. Some authors (Hartig *et al.* 2022) mentioned that incomplete phase transitions from confinement effects, PCM leaching or supercooling can influence the result. However, transparent wood-PCM composites demonstrated enthalpies proportional to polyethylene glycol (PEG) fraction, aligning with rule-of-mixtures prediction when PCM domains remain large enough for bulk-like melting (Montanary *et al.* 2019). Presuming that the bioPCM is stable in the solid wood and leaching eliminated, an attempt was carried out to predict the latent heat in solid wood lamellae by a comparative thermal analysis of bioPCM-impregnated vs. non-impregnated samples.

Samples with known impregnation history, density, WPG and retention were glued in blocks of 9 × 90 × 90 mm (Figure 21) to mimic a fragment of middle-lamella layer in parquet. Ethyl palmitate impregnated samples and a control wood sample without bioPCM were insulated by 20 mm thick material Armaflex (Armacell, Germany) and thermocouples (K-type) placed in the middle of the samples to measure the temperature changes. The impregnated and control samples were placed in a climate chamber and the temperature recorded during steps of 525 min, oscillating between 5 and 35°C to cover the phase change transition of the bioPCM ethyl palmitate.

Figure 21. Scots pine sapwood lamellae impregnated with ethyl palmitate at various retentions.

Data on the impregnated lamellae, retention of EP, measured and calculated melting enthalpy are shown in Table 6, Figures 22 and 23.

Table 6. Impregnation characteristics and enthalpy of the lamellae with ethyl palmitate.

Sample nr.	Weight wood, g	Impregnated EP, g	Weight lamella, g	% of EP	Entalpy of pure EP, J/g	Calculated entalpy, J/g	Measured entalpy, J/g
190	59.8	58	117.8	49	213.4	105.1	104
33	70	47	117	40	213.4	85.7	86
140	66.8	49,8	116.6	43	213.4	91.1	86
70	74	41.8	115.8	36	213.4	77.0	67
155	67.1	48	115.1	42	213.4	89.0	84

The enthalpy of pure ethyl palmitate is adopted from Deliverable 4.8 where the bioPCM was characterised before delivery to SLU for testing. Figure 22 demonstrates temperature vs. time curves under controlled conditions change of the lamellae temperature while Figure 23 shows the development of enthalpy during cooling and heating. The lamella without EP (Figure 22, grey line) shows that thermal energy is stored and released as sensible heat during the heating and cooling cycles, in line with previous observations (Nazari *et al.* 2023; Grzybek *et al.* 2023).

The impregnated EP in the lamellae demonstrated latent heat storage during the phase transition, while energy is still stored and released as sensible heat before and after phase transition. Apparently, the enthalpy of the lamellae with EP depends on the retention, which is proved by the highest enthalpy of 104 J/g by 49% uptake of EP in lamella nr. 190 (Figure 23, blue line). The lowest enthalpy of 67 J/g was measured for sample nr. 70 (black line) with lowest uptake of 36% EP. The other three lamellae have similar retention of 40% (nr. 33), 42% (nr. 155) and 43% (nr. 140) ranked in Figure 23 in descent order as green (nr. 33), yellow (nr. 140) and red (nr. 155).

The values of melting enthalpy and retention of EP are plotted in Figure 24 to demonstrate that the calculated and measured values (regression lines) are close with high regression coefficient of 0.93 for the measured line.

Figure 22. Thermal behaviour by T-history curves of five Scots pine sapwood lamellae impregnated with ethyl palmitate.

Figure 23. Freezing and melting enthalpy calculated by T-history measurements of five Scots pine sapwood lamellae impregnated with ethyl palmitate.

Figure 24. Regression lines of calculated and measured enthalpy of Scots pine lamellae impregnated with ethyl palmitate.

Normalized measured enthalpy uncertainty was found to be 9.7% (Nazari *et al.* 2022) which supports the conclusion that the measured values are within the above interval (apart from sample nr.70) and justified the study approach. Additionally, the measured and predicted values were compared by ANOVA's Tukey's test to find no significant difference between the groups.

5. Impregnation of wood fibres

5.1 Light microscopy study on impregnated wood fibres

Wood is built of various cells that have specified functions, e.g., tracheids in the softwoods ensure conduction and support, vessels are the porous conduits in hardwoods, parenchyma cells are designed for storage while rays are the radial transport paths in the material. The term “*wood fibres*” is simplified, comprehensive and accepted way to describe the diverse wood anatomical elements, meaning primarily the elongated wood cells, which are representing the structural complexity of xylem tissue. Fibre types and wood particles of interest for the projects have been studied and discussed in Deliverable 2.1.

The size of ethyl palmitate (21.6 Å length and 5 Å width, Deliverable 2.2) makes its penetration through the wood cell difficult if not impossible. This is because S_2 layer of softwood cell wall has 3 nm characteristic size of the nano-pores when swollen with water, while the pores shrink (< 1 nm) when the wood cell wall is dried (Digaitis *et al.* 2025). It is exactly the case in the project where the *fibres must be dried prior to impregnation* to evacuate the water from the cell lumen that is filled later with bioPCM. Drying of softwood is accompanied by aspiration (closure) of the bordered pits, which drastically decreases the penetration paths for liquids in the consequent impregnation. Another explanation is the complex structure of the wood cell wall consisting of microfibrils encapsulated with lignin and arrayed at various microfibrillar angles in the sub-layers of the cell wall. An important aspect of using fibres as containers for impregnation of bioPCM is the surface area of the material. As already demonstrated in Deliverable 2.1, the drawback of using CTMP fibres is 24.7% leached ethyl palmitate. The surplus of EP after impregnation is partly located in the cell lumen, but the prevailing part is on the fiber surface which makes it easier to leach. The excess of EP can further aggravate the adhesion of binder to the fibers, e.g., epoxidized linseed oil or lignin and influence the process of polymerization. Moreover, the EP excess can negatively influence the growth of fungal mycelia in the process of using it as a natural binder in the bio-composites – the above has been already discussed and considered in Deliverable 2.1.

How does ethyl palmitate penetrate in the cell lumens under impregnation? The intent of the study in the present Deliverable 2.3 is to discover the penetration paths of the bioPCM into the cell lumen and explain the impregnation of a single fibre. Chemical thermomechanical pulp (CTMP) fibres were impregnated with ethyl palmitate according to the technology in Deliverable 2.1. The chemical pre-treatment of fibres makes fibres easier the refining while partially removing lignin. The CTMP has excellent bulk properties ensuring long and

flexible fibres. Impregnated fibres were studied by light microscopy. In order to demonstrate the presence of ethyl palmitate in the fibres, Oil Red O and osmium tetroxide (OsO_4) were used as dyes to visualise the impregnated bioPCM because they react strongly with double bonds in the carbonyl group in esters and unsaturated triglycerides, i.e., they colour the ethyl palmitate to be seen by microscopy. The observations were done by Leica DMLB light microscope (Leica, Wetzlar, Germany). No additional treatments to the fibres were applied. An illustration of ethyl palmitate crystals as such and impregnated in wood fibres is shown in [Figure 25](#).

Figure 25. Osmium tetroxide staining of frozen ethyl palmitate crystals ([Figure 25a, b](#)), impregnated Scots pine tracheid ([c](#)), birch ([d](#)) and beech ([e](#)) fibres.

Ethyl palmitate is observed in the cell lumen (the empty space inside the cell) as well as crystals on the surface ([Figure 25e](#)). [Figure 26](#) shows various patterns of control and impregnated Scots pine, birch and poplar fibres. Since the hypothesis of EP penetration through the pores in the cell wall was adopted, bordered and simple pits ([Figure 26a, b](#)) are seen as paths for impregnation of bioPCM in the fibres. The impregnated EP can be found as droplets or filled in a part of the lumen or in the entire lumen while some part of the EP was found on the fibre surface ([Figure 26g](#)). The variation in filling the lumen is high and depends probably on several factors, e.g., proportion of opened and aspirated pits, damage in the cell wall and tears of the fibre. An illustration of transport of ethyl palmitate through the opened bordered pits of Scots pine tracheid is shown in [Figure 27](#). Two additional photo pictures of Scots pine fibre tips with partly filled lumens and characteristic intrusions of ethyl palmitate through the pits in forms small to large bubbles are shown in [Figure 28](#).

Figure 26. Control unimpregnated Scots pine tracheids with bordered pits (a) and simple pits in the cross field within a ray (b). Oil Red O staining of CTMP Scots pine tracheids filled with ethyl palmitate in form of droplets (c and d), part of the lumen (e) and the entire lumen (f) impregnated/occupied with EP. Oil Red O staining of CTMP birch vessel with droplets of EP on the surface (g) and poplar vessel and fibre impregnated with EP (h).

Figure 27. Oil Red O staining of CTMP Scots pine tracheid filled with ethyl palmitate, in a process of exudation through bordered pits (Figure 27a-e) and higher magnification of the two pits with spots of ethyl palmitate (f) and in the pit apertures (arrows in f). Scots pine tracheid with ethyl palmitate on the fibre surface (Figure 27g), on the pit borders and in the pit apertures.

Figure 28. Oil Red O staining of the tips of Scots pine tracheids partly filled with ethyl palmitate and a variety of intruded ethyl palmitate through the pits.

Melted and OsO_4 stained ethyl palmitate in Scots pine tracheids demonstrated a number of convex-shaped droplets with a wetting angle $< 90^\circ$ to the cell wall demonstrated in the photo pictures below.

The observations of impregnated hardwood fibres and vessels are similar to those of Scots pine. Frozen poplar fibres and parenchyma cells are filled crystals of ethyl palmitate as shown in [Figure 29](#).

Figure 29. Unstained frozen ethyl palmitate crystals in impregnated poplar fibre (a) and ray parenchyma cells (b).

The microscopy study of the impregnated fibres demonstrated that the bordered pits are the paths for introduction of bioPCM in the cell empty space (lumens). The large anatomical elements, tracheids, vessels, parenchyma cells and fibres uptake and retain the impregnated bioPCM. It was difficult to study the material

because of the phase transition temperature range of ethyl palmitate (21.5-25.2°C), which keeps the PCM in a mushy state and able to move in/on the fibres. It is concluded that the distribution and patterns of filling the cell lumens vary depending on the fibre type and physical condition and it is not applicable to quantify the amount of PCM in the anatomical elements by microscopy.

5.2 Continuum modelling of wood fibre impregnation

Based on the conclusions of the microscopy study and the results in Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2, a computational fluid mechanics (CFD) model was developed to analyse the EP flow rate and distribution after entering the lumen through the pit aperture. Simulations were carried out for spruce (*Picea abies* (L.) Karst.) early- and latewood tracheids called further “fibres”.

The development of the CFD-models was conducted by the commercial software COMSOL Multiphysics® (v6.3, COMSOL AB, Stockholm, Sweden). Although scarcity of literature information about this modelling approach in the area, some previous publications that have analysed fluid transport in pits such as Schulte 2012 and Xu *et al.* 2020 were found. While these CFD models provide important insights into viscous flow and geometric controls on pit-scale resistance, they are limited to single-phase, steady-state liquid flow and neglect the effects of surface tension and capillary pressure. Such effects are expected to become increasingly important at the micro scale and sub-micrometre pore scale of the margo, where capillary forces may be comparable to or exceed viscous forces, and where air seeding, embolism formation, and partial pore saturation can fundamentally alter flow pathways. Consequently, the role of capillary-driven flows and interfacial stresses in regulating pit conductivity remains uncertain.

5.2.1 Governing equations

Liquid penetration of EP in a single wood fibre was analysed with continuum modelling. Lagrangian-Euler two phase flow method called the Level-Set (LS) model was applied to study simultaneous liquid penetration and air removal from the fibre lumen. The LS model tracks the interface of the immiscible fluids based on a partial differential equation describing the transport of the LS-parameter based on advection and diffusion according to the equation (6).

$$\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla \varphi = \gamma \nabla \cdot \left(\epsilon_{ls} \nabla \varphi - \varphi(1 - \varphi) \frac{\nabla \varphi}{|\nabla \varphi|} \right) \quad (6)$$

The velocity field in the LS-equation is solved using the continuity and the Navier-Stokes (NS) equations.

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \rho \nabla \cdot u = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \rho(u \cdot \nabla)u = \nabla \cdot [-pI + \mu(\nabla u + \nabla u^T)] + F \quad (8)$$

In order to use equations (6-8), the continuum assumption must be respected regarding the length scale of the computational domain. Given that the domain is a single wood fiber, the pit aperture is used as the basis for this analysis. The Knudsen (Kn) number, representing the ratio between the molecular mean free path of a gas and a characteristic physical length scale, serves as a criterion for determining whether continuum models remain valid.

$$Kn = \frac{\lambda}{L_c} \quad (9)$$

Here, the characteristic length of the physical model corresponds to the pit aperture diameter. The Knudsen number (Kn) for air indicates that continuum models are valid; however, the Kn value also suggests that a slip boundary condition should be applied at the wood cell wall.

5.2.2 Initial and boundary conditions

The geometrical features of a bordered pit are illustrated in Figure 30. The liquid penetration and air removal were modeled in a 2-dimensional axial symmetric reference frame where one single pit aperture was analyzed (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Two-dimensional representation of the single pit chamber. Lefthand image represents the entire geometry including the lumen of the fiber. The righthand image is an enlarged representation of a bordered pit including the pit aperture, pit membrane consisting of torus and margo, and the wood cell wall.

The margo and the wood cell wall are modelled as porous media, with Darcy’s law used to relate the volume-averaged velocity to the pressure gradient governing the flow rate.

$$\langle u_i \rangle = - \frac{\kappa_{ij}}{\mu} \nabla(pI) \quad (10)$$

where κ_{ij} is permeability of the porous domain and μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid. Thus, Darcy’s law expresses the flow resistance of the material’s complex microstructure through this effective relationship.

The EP is induced by pressure on the upstream boundary in the pit aperture to enter the pit chamber (Figure 31). Wetted cell wall conditions in Figure 31 were set at the boundaries surrounding the lumen (except the axial symmetry boundary). The wetted cell wall function provides a simplified approach to account for shear stress through a slip condition, where the gas phase interacts not directly with the solid cell wall but with a thin intervening liquid layer.

Figure 31. External boundaries assigned to the axis of symmetry and the pressure inlet (left) and external boundaries representing the wetted wall condition (right).

Both the margo and the cell wall are modelled as porous media; hence, the flow properties within the pore space are volume-averaged together with those of the solid matrix. In the case of the margo, both air and ethyl palmitate (EP) exhibit high penetrability. In contrast, the cell wall is assumed to be impermeable to the EP, and internal wall boundaries are therefore applied (Figure 31). The resulting restriction of EP (and air) penetration into the cell wall is considered to have a negligible influence on the overall outcome.

The initial air pressure was set to one hundred-thousandth of the standard atmospheric pressure at 20°C to approximate vacuum conditions. Initially, the pit chamber and lumen were filled with air, while the upstream channel contained the ethyl palmitate.

5.2.3 Case study

Required material data for the simulations were viscosity, density, and in the case for two-phase flow systems, the surface tension was taken from Deliverable 2.2 where ethyl palmitate is described in detail. The employed characteristics of ethyl palmitate were its density (0.860 g/cm³), viscosity 3.197mPa.s) and surface tension (0.0305 N/m). Standard air characteristics are found in COMSOLs database.

Dimensions of Norway spruce cell wall and bordered pits were analyzed based on geometrical features representing early- and latewood and shown in Table 7. The dimensions were selected from the studies of Saren *et al.* (2001), Zimmermann (1983), Siau (1984), Stamm (1964), Brändström (2001), Rosner *et al.* (2007) and Mayr *et al.* (2003) with data on the dimensions of Norway spruce cell wall and bordered pits; the results are illustrated in Figure 32 and summarized in Table 7, which was adopted and modified from a study of Terziev *et al.* (2021).

Figure 32. Schematic illustration of spruce cell wall and a bordered pit (adopted from Terziev *et al.* 2021) with characteristic dimensions shown in [Table 7](#).

Table 7. Data on cell wall and bordered pit dimensions (μm) of Norway spruce. Cell wall density 1.53 g/cm^3 , density of cellulose 1.55 g/cm^3 (adopted from Terziev *et al.* 2021 with modifications).

	Minimum	Maximum	Average
<i>Cell wall thickness CW</i>			
Earlywood	2.8	3.5	3.2
Latewood	3.2	5.0	4.1
<i>Pit chamber diameter D</i>			
Earlywood	10	25	17.5
Latewood	10	15	12.5
<i>Pit chamber aperture d_a</i>			
Earlywood	1.4	5.0	3.2
Latewood	1.4	5.0	3.2
<i>Pit chamber width H_c in earlywood is adopted as cell wall thickness $\times 2$; for latewood it is equal to the cell wall thickness</i>			
Earlywood	$2.8 \times 2 = 5.6$	$3.5 \times 2 = 7.0$	6.3
Latewood	3.2	5.0	4.1
<i>Torus diameter d (twice as large as aperture diameter d_a; (Siau, 1984), i.e. $d = 2d_a$)</i>			
Earlywood	2.8	10	6.4
Latewood	2.8	10	6.4
<i>Torus thickness H</i>			
Earlywood	0.2	1.0	0.6
Latewood	0.3	1.2	0.75
<i>Margo diameter D</i>			
Earlywood	10	25	17.5
Latewood	10	15	12.5
<i>Margo thickness h</i>			
Earlywood	0.1	0.5	0.2
Latewood	0.1	0.5	0.2
<i>Openings in margo, M</i>			
Earlywood			0.25
Latewood			0.25
<i>Tracheid length</i>			
Earlywood	1500	3700	3500
Latewood	1700	4100	3800
<i>Number of bordered pits</i>			

Earlywood		50	300	180
Latewood		10	50	30

5.2.4 Simulation outcome

Data from the numerical simulations are presented in [Figures 33 and 34](#), which illustrate the velocity and pressure distributions in the pit chamber. Under a driving pressure of 6 bars, the velocity reaches roughly 17 m/s at the pit aperture, with an overall pressure drop of about 4.75 bar across the chamber.

Figure 33. Velocity and pressure profile of ethyl palmitate in the pit chamber.

Figure 34. Velocity and pressure profile of ethyl palmitate in the margo and the wood cell wall.

The corresponding volume flow rate and accumulation of ethyl palmitate in early- and latewood fibers are presented in [Figures 35](#), [Figure 36](#) and [Table 8](#). The Figures illustrate the total accumulated amount of ethyl palmitate and the fraction of the lumen volume it occupies, while the Table summarizes the steady-state volumetric flow rate. For earlywood fibre, it takes approximately 5 s to reach the maximum accumulated ethyl palmitate level, whereas for latewood fibre the same level is achieved within 1.5 s.

Figure 35. Time evolution of ethyl palmitate accumulation and filling ratio in an earlywood fibre. Accumulation refers to the proportion of the lumen volume filled with ethyl palmitate.

Figure 36. Time evolution of ethyl palmitate accumulation and filling ratio in a latewood fibre. Accumulation refers to the proportion of the lumen volume filled with ethyl palmitate.

Table 8. Modelled uptake of ethyl palmitate in early- and latewood fibres of Norway spruce.

	Flow rate, $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	Accumulated EP, μL
Earlywood fibre	5.70	4.68
Latewood fibre	5.44	2.99

Surface tension is defined at the interface of the two immiscible fluids (air and ethyl palmitate), but its mechanical effects can be represented and integrated over a volume containing the interface. Figures 37 and 38 present the volume-averaged surface tension force in the lumen for early- and latewood fibre respectively. The Figures show that the steady-state surface tension coincides with the maximum steady-state volume occupied by ethyl palmitate. This suggests that the applied pressure should be increased during the impregnation process to overcome the rising surface tension and thereby enhance the filling ratio in the cell lumen.

Figure 37. Volume-averaged surface tension in the lumen of an earlywood fiber.

Figure 38. Volume-averaged surface tension in the lumen of a latewood fiber.

The simulations revealed clear differences between early- and latewood fibre impregnation behaviour arising from pit geometry and flow resistance. Accumulation of ethyl palmitate that shows the proportion of the lumen volume filled with liquid was found to be ca. 47% in the earlywood fiber and ca. 60% in the latewood fiber. This supports the calculations in D2.1 where it was found that significant part of the ethyl palmitate is on the fiber surface and thus, susceptible to leaching. Importantly, the surface tension and capillary effects increased as lumen filling progressed and significantly influenced the impregnation efficiency. This suggests that induced pressure should increase during the impregnation to overcome rising surface tension. These results show that interfacial forces, neglected in single-phase models, play a key role in regulating pit-scale transport and should be considered when analysing or designing wood fibre impregnation processes. The original approach of the study applies a two-phase model to simulate liquid penetration, incorporating the effect of air pressure despite its low density. As a result, capillary forces become a critical aspect to consider.

Performed multiple simulations of individual fibers and post-process data (video and images) are available.

6. Overall conclusions by Deliverables 2.1-2.3 to be considered further in the project

Work package 2 and Deliverables D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3 are the technological basis of the project BIOBUILD. Deliverable 2.1 selected and tested four wood species and seven types of fibers and wood particles to demonstrate the effect of thermal and microwave modification on the wood porosity. The increase in wood porosity was proven by picnometry, X-ray computer tomography, scanning electron microscopy and retention of ethyl palmitate in the modified materials. The above treatments had limited effect on the leaching of the impregnated bioPCM.

Deliverable 2.2 studied and selected impregnation schedules for the materials. The approach in the selection of impregnation schedules was empirical and within realistic practical limits, e.g., pressure and duration, that are used in the impregnation industry.

Deliverable 2.3 modelled the impregnation process. The statistical modelling used the linear relationship between solid wood density and pretention of liquid and found that the optimal impregnation pressure was 6 bars and duration of 30 min. Higher pressure serves as well but provokes higher leaching. Regarding leaching, it was found that it can be decreased by selection of impregnation parameters, but it cannot be eliminated. The reason is the physical nature of the bioPCM (ethyl palmitate), which is non-polar and is held in the capillary of the porous material only by physical forces.

Washburn equation-based modelling supported by X-ray computer tomography of solid wood allowed to calculate the amount of the impregnated ethyl palmitate as a function of pressure and time. The model is of practical importance because it can predict the impregnated amount by the impregnation parameters. The model is also applicable to a number of wood species; it considers the effect of pre-treatments of solid wood. Both statistical and Washburn equation-based models showed good fit with experimental data and can be used for practical impregnation of ethyl palmitate. The amount of impregnated ethyl palmitate is positively correlated to the melting enthalpy of the bioPCM.

A computational fluid mechanics model was used to demonstrate the impregnation of EP in a single spruce fiber. The simulations revealed clear differences between early- and latewood fibre impregnation behaviour arising from pit geometry and flow resistance. Importantly, the surface tension and capillary effects increased as lumen filling progressed and significantly influenced the impregnation efficiency.

The selected bioPCM, i.e., ethyl palmitate in Deliverable 4.8 was applied throughout the work in WP2 and the Deliverables D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3 contributed to the understanding of the practical impregnation of solid wood lamellae for parquet and wood particles for bio-composites with the three binders in the project. The results of WP2 were used further in the work of WP3 and WP4 and their deliverables. The work in WP2 was carried out in collaboration between CNR, SLU, PCMP and UDL.

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Appendix

Impregnation model (A) and calibration data (B).

Lucas-Washburn type model for liquid penetration - adapted for wood impregnation ("bulk" flow)

Cells with thin border are model parameters
 Cells with darker background color must be manually entered

$$V_d = \frac{\pi}{16} \left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=d_{max}}^{i=d} d_i^2 \cdot \sqrt{\left(P_E + \frac{4\gamma}{d_i} \cos\theta \right) \cdot (d_i^2 + 8 \cdot \varepsilon(t) \cdot d_i)}$$

input

Pressure	P_E	3 bar	30591,48 Kg/m ²
Time	t	30 minutes	1800 s

output

Filled porosity (%)	Retention (kg/m ³)	Impregnation (%)	Filled pore size: >than μ m
43,95	377,94	74,22%	20,11
$V_d \cdot 100 / 1 m^3$			d

Wood Pore Size Distribution (from X-ray micro-CT)

Image resolution (voxel size) **3,25** μ m
 # of size class **10**

Pore size μ m	Porosity* %	Cumulated porosity %	
65	0,000791	0,000791	0,076396
58,5	0,00358	0,004371	0,057533
52	0,012898	0,017268	0,041967
45,5	0,111772	0,12904	0,029404
39	1,76797	1,89701	0,019647
32,5	11,57745	13,47446	0,012097
26	18,80317	32,27763	0,006752
19,5	12,88142	45,15905	0,003203
13	12,32713	57,48617	0,00113
6,5	1,727664	59,21384	0,000194
0	0	0	

* (!) Pore size % distribution reported from the largest to the smallest pore size class (middle diameter)

Impregnant liquid properties (Ethyl palmitate)

EP density 20°C	0,86 g/cm ³	860 kg/m ³
EP surface tension	30,5 dyne/cm	0,0305 kg/s ²
EP viscosity 70°C	2,214 mPa·s	0,002214 kg/(m·s)

Wood-Impregnant interaction parameters

$\cos(\theta)$ **-0,5** $\cos(\theta)$ varying in the range [-1, 1]; θ is the "apparent" contact angle liquid/solid

slip coefficient $\varepsilon(t)$ **0,012428** $\varepsilon(t) = a \cdot \exp(-b \cdot t)$ obtained by model calibration from experimental tests

Calibration data (bar)

	a	b	here obtained from experimental tests on Scots pine wood
3	0,0315	0,031	
6	0,0404	0,062	
current	0,0315	0,031	

Slip coefficient (LW model)

Liquid properties					B
*	EP density	0,86 g/cm ³	860 kg/m ³		
*	EP surface	30,5 dyne/cm	0,0305 kg/s ²		
*	EP viscosit	2,214 mPa*s	0,002214 kg/(m*s)		

Experimental data of impregnation

P	t	EP retentic filled pore vol		Vol ret	t	(t/visc)^1/2	epsilon (t)*
bar	min	kg/m ³	m ³ /m ³ (%)	lt/m ³	(sec)		
3	15	190	0,2209	221	900	637,5767	0,019602
3	30	375	0,4360	436	1800	901,6696	0,012335
3	45	400	0,4651	465	2700	1104,315	0,007625
6	15	410	0,4767	477	900	637,5767	0,015782
6	30	440	0,5116	512	1800	901,6696	0,006315
6	45	450	0,5233	523	2700	1104,315	0,002439

* values determined by matching model output with experimental results

